

Making carbon farming work in practice: Insights from ECFS 2026

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As Europe moves from designing carbon farming frameworks to implementing them in practice, the discussions at the European Carbon Farming Summit (ECFS 2026) reflected a field entering a more operational phase. Across three days of discussions, participants explored some of the central challenges facing carbon farming today, including financing, demand creation, robust monitoring systems, and the integration of broader environmental and social outcomes. One message emerged clearly: scaling carbon farming will depend not only on credible methodologies, but also on the ability to align policy, finance, science, and practice within workable systems.

This year’s European Carbon Farming Summit (ECFS 2026), held from 17–19 March in Padua, brought together over 700 participants in person, alongside a wider online audience. As in previous years, the Summit convened policymakers, researchers, businesses, and farmers from across Europe. The event also featured high-level representatives from the European Commission and related sectors, including Kurt

Vandenberghe, Christian Holzleitner, Elisabeth Werner, and other leading voices working at the intersection of climate policy, finance, agriculture, and land use.

This time, however, the focus of the discussion shifted towards financing and implementation. Across sessions, conversations were more direct, often more technical, and built on work already underway, while also highlighting the main areas that still require clarification.

As Christian Holzleitner, Head of Unit for Land Economy and Carbon Removals at DG CLIMA, noted:

“Europe is entering a decisive phase in the implementation of the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Regulation. The focus is now on ensuring that carbon farming delivers measurable climate impact while creating real value for farmers and land managers.”

A shifting context

The Summit opened against a backdrop that is becoming harder to ignore. As noted by Climate KIC CEO Kirsten Dunlop, the polycrisis is not only environmental, but also social and economic, and for these reasons, truly systemic. Climate risks are accelerating, while economic pressures and political uncertainty complicate the pace and direction of response.

In this context, incremental change is insufficient. Discussions returned repeatedly to the need for approaches that can shift entire systems, rather than optimise individual components. The idea of creating positive tipping points came up more than once, particularly in relation to land use, where changes in practice, finance, and policy need to move together.

Carbon as a tool for more holistic approaches

One of the threads throughout the Summit was a reframing of carbon itself. It is no longer being treated as the objective, but as a way of structuring action. Used in this way, carbon provides a common reference point that can support coordination across different actors and outcomes. From there, the discussion naturally broadens to include soil health, biodiversity, water systems, and longer-term farm, forest, and landscape resilience.

This shift was reflected in the strong demand for practical examples. Participants were less interested in models or projections, and more in demonstrations that show how integrated approaches can work under real conditions, across different regions and production systems.

At the same time, a number of sessions highlighted the limits of treating carbon in isolation. More integrated approaches to land management are increasingly seen as necessary, both to improve outcomes and to make participation more viable.

One issue is the cost of monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV), particularly for smaller landholders. Clustering approaches were discussed as a way to reduce these costs and reach sufficient scale. Models such as Landscape Enterprise Networks (LENs) were cited as useful examples, particularly for their ability to operate at landscape scale and connect land managers with supply chains and funders within a shared framework.

More broadly, connections between land use and the bioeconomy remain underdeveloped. In forestry, for example, carbon storage can be considered not only in standing biomass, but also in how wood is used and how long carbon remains stored in products. Ensuring sustainable forest management while maximising long-term carbon storage in wood products remains both necessary and challenging.

Carbon, biodiversity, and water credits are typically treated separately, yet in practice they are closely linked. Whether these should be bundled into single certificates, combined through stacking approaches, or coordinated via shared methodologies remains an open question.

Financing: bringing sources into alignment

Finance is no longer discussed in abstract terms. There is now a shared recognition that existing funding structures are too fragmented to support the transition at scale. A central issue is the synergetic relations between public funding and private investment. The additionality principle, essential in certain contexts, can make it challenging to combine the two, particularly where public subsidies are already available. As a result, funding streams often operate in parallel rather than in coordination.

At the Summit, many conversations revolved around how these sources can be aligned. The Buyers' Club, proposed by the European Commission, was discussed in this context, not only as a way to stimulate demand, but also as a mechanism that could help structure participation from both public and private actors.

Alongside this, participants pointed to the need for a new kind of intermediary. A finance orchestrator, able to coordinate different funding sources and align incentives across stakeholders without favouring any single group.

The demand gap

While the design of the supply side of carbon farming has advanced in recent years, the demand side has not kept pace. This imbalance was a recurring theme throughout the Summit and is now seen as one of the main constraints on further development.

The Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation is expected to provide a foundation for trust and standardisation, but it does not in itself create demand. That gap is now becoming more visible as certification methodologies mature and enter operationalisation.

The abovementioned Buyers' Club is one response to this, although its design and scope remain under discussion. Questions raised during the Summit included how demand might be coordinated across value chains, how different types of carbon farming activities should be distinguished, and how voluntary markets, which on their own are unlikely to move the needle, could connect with effective compliance mechanisms.

Examples from existing systems were used to ground this discussion. France's *Label Bas Carbone*, for instance, links voluntary carbon projects to regulatory demand requirements in specific sectors. Looking ahead, there is growing interest in whether similar approaches could be developed at EU level, including possible links to ETS2 for emissions that are difficult to abate.

These are not yet settled questions, but they are likely to shape the next phase of work.

MRV as the operational backbone

One of the clearest messages from the Summit was that MRV is not a technical issue. It is becoming the operational backbone of carbon farming in Europe. This was reflected not only in Plenary Session 4 on risk and uncertainty, but also in the Summit programme itself, which identified "Building robust and flexible MRV" as one of the five core themes and dedicated numerous sessions to baselines, carbon modelling, Earth Observation, data sharing, harmonisation, and certification.

The discussions showed that uncertainty in carbon sequestration begins well before certification. It arises through baseline design, model structure, remote sensing, soil sampling, and assumptions about future outcomes. The central challenge is therefore not to eliminate uncertainty entirely, but to quantify it, communicate it transparently, and manage it in ways that preserve both credibility and economic viability. This was a recurring point in Plenary Session 4, where MRV was closely linked to liability, insurance, and investment risk.

A second strong message concerned the importance of public data, harmonised baselines, and shared infrastructures. Across the Summit, participants stressed that credible MRV must also be practical and affordable, particularly for farmers and smaller landholders. What emerged was a more mature understanding of MRV: not simply as a control mechanism, but as an enabling infrastructure that underpins trust, lowers transaction costs, and makes broader implementation possible.

A community taking shape

Beyond the technical discussions, the Summit reflected a broader shift in the way the European carbon farming community is evolving. Conversations are becoming more focused, and while disagreements remain, there is less divergence in how issues are framed. A more common language is beginning to emerge, which makes it easier to engage with the more complex aspects of implementation.

This does not resolve the underlying challenges, but it does suggest a field that is moving from exploration towards consolidation.

Reflecting on this transition, Climate KIC CEO Kirsten Dunlop emphasised:

“Carbon farming will only scale if it is credible, economically viable, and grounded in the realities and needs of farmers and land managers.”

What happens next

The 2026 Summit anticipates the end of the current phase of the Horizon Europe-funded CREDIBLE project. Over the past three years, the project has played a central role in building a shared foundation across policy, science, and practice.

This work will continue under a new phase of the CREDIBLE project, with a renewed consortium and a continued focus on implementation. Preparations for the 2027 Summit are already underway, including the selection of a new co-hosting organisation and location. In parallel, the outcomes of this year's Summit are being taken forward. Recommendations from each session¹ have been consolidated and will be shared with the European Commission, with the aim of informing the next stages of policy development and implementation.

About the European Carbon Farming Summit

The European Carbon Farming Summit is an annual gathering driving Europe's transition towards credible and scalable carbon farming.

This year's Summit was organised by SAE Innova and Climate KIC as part of the Project CREDIBLE consortium and co-hosted by EIT Food (as LILAS4SOILS coordinator) and Confagricoltura Veneto, with the support of Veneto Agricoltura.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/20343045>